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Empirical Research of Teaching British Communicative Behavior Patterns in English Classes

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Abstract: *This article outlines the design, implementation, and results of an experimental study aimed at teaching British communicative behavior patterns in English classes. The experiment was conducted to assess the effectiveness of specific teaching methodologies and strategies in enhancing students' understanding and application of British communicative norms in practice. It discusses the research objectives, methodology, instructional design, data collection methods, and the results, including an analysis of student performance and feedback.*

Key words: *communicative behavior, pragmatic competence, cultural knowledge, instructions, authentic material.*

Introduction.

Nowadays in construction of foreign language teaching programmes the priority is given to development of pragmatic competence that covers pragmalinguistic and sociocultural or intercultural aspects of language operating (Kramsch 1995, Yule 1996, Makhkamova 2010). It is known that pragmatic research aims to study of speech acts and communicative strategies functions in dependence of the context (situational and cultural) (Yule 1996, Makhkamova 2019). Thus, it is important to master pragmatic competence that related to intercultural awareness about communicative behavior of the native speakers and allows to preventing misunderstanding in intercultural communication (Canale & Swain 1980; Yule 1996; Thornbury 2006, Brown 2007; Makhkamova 2019). In the mentioned angle this article is devoted to description of the empirical study organization in the context of teaching British communicative behavior in the English classes. For this purpose achievements the following research objectives are formulated:

1. To evaluate the effectiveness of integrating cultural knowledge into language instruction: revealing the influence of cultural factors on communicative behavior organizing.

2. To assess the level of pragmatic competence in the context of using polite speech formulas and indirect speech acts: evaluating students' proficiency in employing various linguistic structures that convey politeness and respect in conversations (see: Yule 1996, Makhkamova 2019).
3. To examine the role of authentic materials and technology in enhancing students' learning experiences: analysis of how the use of media and digital tools influences students' engagement and understanding of the British communicative rules and conventions.
4. To measure students' intercultural awareness about national specificity of the British communicative behavior in comparison with the native culture: understanding of how British communicative behavior differs from their own cultural norms.

Methodology

Participants

The study involved 60 undergraduate students enrolled in an English language course at BA department of Tashkent state pedagogical university. The participants have diverse cultural backgrounds to provide a rich context for analyzing differences in communicative behavior. The students were divided into two groups: an experimental group (28 students) that received targeted instruction on British communicative behavior patterns and a control group (32 students) that followed the standard English curriculum without a specific focus on cultural nuances.

Instructional Design

Based on the experience in development of intercultural competence and speech acts (Kramsch 1993, Thornbury 2006, Brown 2007, Makhkamova 2010, 2019), the instructional input for the experimental group was design through combination of several educational strategies:

- **Cultural Knowledge Integration:** The programme included lessons on British politeness strategies, indirect speech acts, and different contexts or situations of communication. Instructional materials were drawn from various sources, including academic articles, videos, and real-life scenarios.
- **Pragmatic Competence Development:** Lessons focused on speech acts, including making requests, giving feedback, and handling disagreements. Case study (cross-cultural situations), role-playing activities and simulations were incorporated to allow students to practice these speech acts in a certain context.
- **Use of Authentic Materials:** British films, television shows, and online resources were utilized to expose students to real-life examples of British communication patterns. Analysis of dialogues and discussions on cultural nuances were integral to the instructional activities.
- **Technology Integration:** Digital tools, such as language learning apps and virtual conversation simulations, were used to reinforce learning. These tools provided interactive experiences where students could practice their communicative skills in simulated environments.

Data Collection Methods

Data were collected through a combination of quantitative and qualitative methods:

- **Pre- and Post-Tests:** Students in both the experimental and control groups took a pre-test before the intervention and a post-test at the end of the course. The tests assessed students' understanding

of British communicative behavior patterns, including their pragmatic skills to use polite expressions and recognize appropriate contexts for various speech acts.

- **Surveys:** Participants completed surveys measuring their perceptions of the instructional methods, engagement levels, and confidence in using British communicative behavior patterns.
- **Observation and Feedback:** Classroom observations were conducted during the experimental group's lessons to gather qualitative data on student participation in interaction and language performance in speaking. Teacher feedback and peer evaluations were also collected to assess the effectiveness of the cases, role-playing and simulation exercises.

Results

Quantitative Results

The pre- and post-test results indicated a significant improvement in the experimental group's understanding and application of British communicative behavior patterns in the situational activities. The average score of the experimental group on the post-test was 85%, compared to an average score of 62% on the pre-test, demonstrating a 23% increase in speaking performance. In contrast, the control group showed only a slight improvement, with post-test scores averaging 65%, indicating that the traditional programme did not significantly enhance their understanding of cultural features of British communication.

Statistical analysis using a paired t-test confirmed the significance of these results ($p < 0.01$), demonstrating that the targeted instruction on British communicative behavior was effective in improving student performance.

Qualitative Feedback

Feedback from student surveys revealed positive responses to the instructional strategies used in the experimental group. The majority of students (85%) reported that the integration of cultural knowledge into the programme enhanced their understanding of British communication. Many students noted that problem-solving cases help understanding the norms and rules of British communicative behavior, in turn, role-playing activities and the use of authentic materials helped them feel more confident in using polite expressions and navigating social contexts in British English.

Observational data indicated that students were actively engaged into role-playing activity, with many students demonstrating increased willingness to participate in discussions about cultural differences in communication. Students expressed a greater appreciation for the subtleties of British politeness and indirectness, with comments such as:

- "I never realized how important it is to be indirect in British communication; it really changes the way you think about conversation."
- "The role plays helped me understand how to politely disagree without offending anyone."

Discussion

The results of this experiment underscore the importance of pragmatic competence development focusing on speech acts, politeness. The significant improvement in the experimental group's understanding of British communicative behavior patterns highlights the effectiveness of proposed instructional strategies. By incorporating problematic situations, role-playing, authentic materials, and technology into the syllabus, students were able to engage more deeply with the cultural nuances of communication.

Furthermore, the positive qualitative feedback from students indicates that such teaching methodologies not only enhance language proficiency but also build intercultural awareness in the framework of pragmatic competence. This awareness is crucial in our increasingly globalized world, where effective communication across cultures is paramount.

The experiment conducted in this study demonstrates that teaching British communicative behavior patterns in English classes is effective when incorporating cultural and linguistic knowledge, and technology. The positive outcomes indicate that students can significantly improve their understanding and application of British communicative norms, which are essential for successful interactions in diverse contexts. These findings suggest that language instructors should prioritize the integration of cultural elements in their teaching practices to foster greater intercultural competence among their students.

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